

THE SLIDING WEAR RESISTANCE BEHAVIOR OF NiAl AND SiC PARTICLES REINFORCED ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The sliding wear resistance behavior of NiAl and SiC particles reinforced aluminum alloy matrix composites against S45C steel was studied. Experiments were performed within a load range of 3.5 N to 82.7 N. At low loads, the wear resistance of the SiCp/Al and NiAlp/Al composites was superior to that of unreinforced aluminum alloy. With increasing the applied load, the wear rates of the composites increased to levels comparable to those of unreinforced matrix alloys. The wear rates of NiAlp/Al and SiCp/Al composites above 13.5 N were much lower than those of aluminum alloy. The wear rates of steel against a aluminum alloy were lower than those against the SiCp/Al composites. The NiAlp/Al composites worn the steel at the maximum wear rate at lower loads near 5 N. As load increased, the wear rates of steel against NiAlp/Al became smaller and were almost the same as those worn against aluminum.

KEYWORDS: particle reinforced metal matrix composites, SiCp/Al composites, NiAlp/Al composites, wear resistance behavior, wear, friction

INTRODUCTION

Particle reinforced metal matrix composites are recognized to have better wear resistance for the presence of hard particle. These materials can be used as a reinforced parts in piston, brake disk and in several wear resistance applications. The tribological behavior of MMCs depends on the type of MMCs, counterface materials and the contact situation.

An increase in the sliding wear resistance of particle or whisker reinforced aluminum alloys has been measured by many researchers in recent years [1-10]. Pramila Bai et al [6] found the fact that SiC particle reinforced A356 aluminum composites improved the wear resistance was attributed to the presence of SiC particles which reduced the propensity for materials flow at the surface, and the formation of iron-rich layers on the surfaces of composite during sliding. However, results of sliding wear conducted by various researchers do not show a consistent trends, Bhansali and Mehrabian [7] found that there was an absence of any significant improvement in wear resistance under abrasive wear conditions for the 20 wt% SiCp/2024Al composite worn against steel. It was attributed to the presence of brittle Al₄C₃ at the interface between particle and matrix. Alpas and Embury [8] showed that under the

conditions where SiC particles promoted subsurface cracking and materials removed by delamination, SiC reinforcement did not contribute to the wear resistance of aluminum alloys.

Recent studies [8-10] revealed that wear resistance was largely affected by the strength of interface between particle and matrix as well as the mechanical properties of the materials. Alpas et al [11-12] found that when particles lose their ability to support the applied load due to particle fracture, interface debonding and pull-out, particle reinforcement may cause no improvement or even a deterioration in the wear properties.

The NiAl particle reinforced aluminum alloy (Al-Ni-Mg-Mn series alloy) composite was considered to have a better interface bonding between particle and matrix and better wear resistance compared with unreinforced aluminum alloy [13]. Besides, since the hardness of NiAl particle is lower than that of SiC particle, it is predicted that the NiAl particle reinforced aluminum composites give the counterface small wear damage. However, the research on the sliding wear resistance of the NiAlp/Al composites worn against the steel was less reported in the existed literature. The purpose of this paper is to understand the sliding wear resistance of the SiCp/Al and NiAlp/Al composites with different volume fraction (5 vol% and 10 vol%) worn against S45C steel, and to study the effects of the applied load and different types of particles on the sliding wear mechanisms.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The experimental apparatus used was a pin-on-disk type tribometer, which was modified in the previous works [14]. A moving lower specimen (disk) and a fixed upper specimen (pin) were mounted at the ends of a driven shaft and a fixed shaft respectively. Normal load was applied to the specimens by a dead weight at the upper end of the fixed shaft supported by two sliding ball bearings. The rotating motion of the fixed shaft induced by frictional torque was restricted by a plate spring on which strain gauges were attached for measuring the frictional torque. The relative distance between the specimens was measured by a dial gauge type displacement transducer placed on a fixed upper specimen. The frictional force and the relative distance were recorded continuously by a recorder. The dry sliding wear tests were carried out at a constant sliding velocity of 0.15 m/s within the applied normal load range of 3.5 N to 82.7 N. The sliding distance was all up to 1000 m.

The disk specimens were made of an aluminum alloy (Al 91.4 %, Ni 3.0 %, Mg 4.8 %, Mn 0.8 %) with or without reinforced particles of NiAl and SiC at volume fraction of 5 vol% and 10 vol% respectively. These alloy and composites were produced by the Ryobe Company in Tokyo, Japan, by means of liquid aluminum alloy stirring method. The dimensions of the disk specimen were a diameter of 19.5 mm and a height of 8 mm which was machined from the rods fabricated by directly die-casting. The average NiAl and SiC particle sizes are 50 and 10 μm respectively, the Vickers hardness of NiAl particle was about 270 Hv. The counterface material used as a fixed pin was 0.45%C steel, S45C, with the Vickers hardness of 225 Hv. The diameter and the length were 4 mm and 8 mm respectively. The mean contacting diameter was 13 mm on the disk specimen. The wear surfaces of the disk and pin specimens were polished by the SiC abrasive papers up to 1000 grits. The polished surfaces were then cleaned ultrasonically in acetone for 15 minute. The center line average surface roughness Ra was 0.2 μm for aluminum alloy, 0.4 μm for NiAlp/Al composite, 0.6 μm for SiCp/Al composite and 0.3 μm for S45C steel respectively.

The weight losses of specimens were measured with an accuracy of 0.1 mg using an electronic analytical balance. The specific wear rates were calculated as the volume loss divided by the sliding distance and the applied load. The results were taken as the average from at least three tests. Microstructural investigations and semi-quantitative chemical analyses on the worn surfaces were performed by SEM and EDXA(energy dispersive X-ray analysis).

RESULTS

The Specific Wear Rates of Aluminum Alloy and Composites

The specific wear rates of the aluminum alloy, the NiAlp/Al and SiCp/Al composites at applied loads from 3.5 N to 82.7 N within the sliding distance of 1000 m are shown in Fig. 1. The specific wear rate of aluminum alloy is decreased with increasing the applied load between 3.5 N to 9.4 N. However, it is increased at the load from 9.4 N to 13.5 N. Severe wear appears above 13.5 N. Large aluminum debris particles were formed at the initial stage of sliding and severe surface damage happened to occur.

At the lowest load of 3.5 N, the wear rate of aluminum alloy is about an order of magnitude larger than those of the SiC and the 10 pct NiAl particle reinforced composites. It reveals that at small loads, aluminum alloy shows lower wear resistance than particle reinforced composites. The wear rate of the 5 pct NiAl particle reinforced composite is in the moderate, about 5 times of those of other composites. The specific wear rate of composites is increased with the load, and at 9.4 N, the specific wear rates of composites are almost close to that of

Fig. 1: The specific wear rate of aluminum alloy, 5 vol% and 10 vol% NiAlp/Al and SiCp/Al composites versus the applied load.

Fig. 2: The coefficient of friction versus the applied load.

Fig. 3: The specific wear rate of S45C steel worn against aluminum alloy and composites versus the applied load after the sliding distance of 1000 m.

unreinforced aluminum alloy, and then, no improvement of wear resistance of composites at this load level. However, above 9.4 N, the specific wear rate of composites decreases with increasing the applied load, even when the applied load is increased to 82.7 N. It reveals that particle reinforced composites have the ability to increase wear resistance at higher loads.

Fig. 1 shows that the NiAlp/Al composites seem to have a litter better wear resistance than the SiCp/Al composites within load range from 5.5 N to 82.7 N, even at the fact that the hardness of NiAl particle is smaller than that of SiC particle. However, at the low load range below 4.5 N, the wear rate of 5 pct NiAlp/Al composite is higher than other composites. Increasing the

volume fraction of particle decreases the wear rate of NiAlp/Al composites. On the contrary, the wear rate of SiCp/Al composites is increased by increasing the volume fraction of particle over the load applied.

The coefficients of friction of aluminum alloy and composites are shown as in Fig. 2. It is obvious that the coefficient of friction between S45C steel and 10 pct NiAlp/Al composite is the largest at the lowest load of 3.5 N, it was above 0.75 and decreased with increasing the load, and then, the coefficient of friction became the same with those of other materials between 0.4 and 0.5 at loads above 9.4 N. Meanwhile, the 5 pct NiAlp/Al composite had the largest coefficient of friction at 4.5 N, however, it drop quickly with increasing the load.

The Specific Wear Rate of the Counterface Materials, S45C Steel

In practical use, it is important to know the total wear of the entire tribological system. The wear rates of the counterface materials S45C steel worn against aluminum alloy, NiAlp/Al and SiCp/Al composites are shown in Fig. 3. The specific wear rate of the steel against aluminum alloy is smaller compared with those against SiCp/Al composites at entire loads and NiAlp/Al composites at load range below 9.4 N. The SiCp/Al composites worn the steel at higher wear rate, especially when the applied loads are above 9.4 N. The wear rates of the steel against SiCp/Al composites are about an order of magnitude larger than those of against NiAlp/Al composites and aluminum alloy at 13.5 N. The wear rates of the steel are increased by the increase of volume fraction of SiC particle.

The specific wear rates of steel against NiAlp/Al composites are affected seriously by change of applied loads. Under the applied loads below 13.5 N, the NiAlp/Al composites worn the steel at a large wear rate. The wear rate of steel reached the maximum at 4.5 N for 5 pct composite and at 5.5 N for 10 pct composite. The maximum wear rate at relatively low loads is about 10-15 times of those at high loads. When the load is above 4.5 N for 5 pct composite and 5.5 N for 10 pct composite, the wear rates begun to drop and finally became the same with those of against aluminum alloy.

DISCUSSION

Wear Resistance at Low Loads

At the lowest applied load, the high wear resistance of SiCp/Al materials is attributed to the presence of SiC particle in the matrix. The particle protrusions are found as high as 6 μm . These protruded particles act as load supporting elements and are useful to prevent the softer aluminum matrix becoming directly involved in the wear process at low loads. The presence of SiC particle is also useful to prevent the matrix aluminum alloy from early fracture at low loads. Fig. 4 shows the coefficient of friction and the relative distance between the surfaces of a pin and a disk for the aluminum alloy (a) and SiCp/Al composite (b) versus the sliding distance at 3.5 N. For aluminum alloy, the coefficient of friction jumps to about two times of the usual value at several sliding distance, meanwhile, the relative distance is also changed abruptly as shown in point A and B in Fig. 4 (a). The increasing of coefficient of friction and the abrupt change in distance may be attributed to the formation of wear particles between surfaces due to the aluminum damaged at the contact surface. However, at the same load for SiCp/Al composite, no such phenomenon could be found as shown in Fig. 4 (b).

Fig. 4: The coefficient of friction and distance change between the contact surface at 3.5 N (a) Aluminum alloy (b) 5 vol% SiCp/Al composite.

The chemical composition of worn surface of the disk is also changed by the presence of SiC particle. Energy dispersive X-ray analyses were performed to determine the relative atomic percentages of metallic elements (Al, Si, and Fe) on the worn surfaces of the SiCp/Al composites at low load. Two typical areas which are full with and without SiC particles were selected. The results reveal that the relative content of Fe element at the surface with SiC particle is larger than that of the surface without SiC particle at 3.5 N. It implies that transfer of Fe element from steel to the surface of the composites is increased by the abrasive action of the presence of SiC particle in the matrix.

The NiAl particle does not stand proud of the surface. It is not able to prevent the softer matrix aluminum alloy directly involved in wear process. As a result, the wear rate of 5 pct NiAlp/Al composite at 3.5 N is about five times of that of the SiCp/Al composites. However, it is still lower than that of unreinforced aluminum alloy because the hardness of NiAl particle is larger than that of aluminum alloy and the particle is not fracture at low loads.

Fig. 5: The worn surface of 10 vol% SiCp/Al composite (a) at 3.5 N showing the SiC particle in structural integrity (b) at 9.4 N.

Wear Resistance at Middle and High Loads

When the load is increased to reach the fracture strength of the particle, the particles begin to fracture and lose their ability to support the load. Fig. 5 (a) shows the SiC particles in structural integrity on the wear surface of the SiCp/Al composite at 3.5 N, it reveals that the particles do not fracture at low loads. However, at the loads higher than 9.4 N, it is very difficult to discover these particles in structural integrity as shown in Fig. 5 (b). The particle near the contact surface may induce the nucleation of crack due to the interface debonding between particle and matrix than monolithic aluminum alloy. In sliding wear process, these cracks may propagate and connect to form the subsurface cracks, the subsurface damage process is increased by the presence of particle. The subsurface crack is also found for the 10 pct SiCp/Al composite as shown in Fig. 6. As a result, when the load increased up to 9.4 N, the wear rates of composites increased to levels comparable to that of the unreinforced aluminum alloy.

When the load is increased above 13.5 N, the wear process of the aluminum alloy may be a deformation and damage accumulation process. The depth of the deformed layers of the aluminum alloy below the worn surfaces is more deeper than that of the composites since the yield strength of the composites is larger. Besides, the surface temperature increased with the applied load and sliding distance. Aluminum alloy is easily to occur thermal softening and recrystallization at high temperature compared with the composites because the strength of the composites at high temperature is greater. As a result, the wear rate of the aluminum alloy is increased drastically at the load higher than 13.5 N. No this transition to severe wear can be found for the composites. However, the deformation and damage of the worn surface is also very obvious. Some of the deformed layer is broken, and several broken particles become fragmented and accumulated as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6: The cross section perpendicular to worn surface of 10 vol% SiCp/Al composite at 40 N showing the subsurface crack is occurred.

The Wear Rate of the Counterface Material at Different Loads

The wear rate of the steel against the SiCp/Al composites is larger than that of against unreinforced aluminum alloy over the load applied for the presence of high hardness of SiC particle in the matrix. It is interesting that even if the hardness of NiAl particle is smaller than that of SiC particle, the wear rate of steel against the NiAlp/Al composite is about twice higher than that against the SiCp/Al composite at low loads near 5 N as shown in Fig. 3. The

Fig. 7: The worn surface of 10 vol% SiCp/Al composite at 64 N (a) showing the tribolayer fractured (b) showing the broken particle fragmented and accumulated.

coefficient of friction versus sliding distance of a NiAlp/Al composite at 3.5 N shows that within the sliding distance of 250 m, the coefficient of friction is only 0.4, then, the coefficient of friction is increased with the sliding distance and reached twice of the initial value. The wear mechanism was changed after the sliding distance of 250 m. The NiAl particle is not stand proud of the contact surface, however, at several meter sliding wear, the soften aluminum alloy was fractured, as a result, the contact surface became the steel and the NiAl particle, the harder NiAl particle could abrade the S45C steel surface, and the NiAl particle wear the steel at very high wear rate. As a result, the coefficient of friction and the weight loss of steel is increased. At low load, the higher intensity of Fe means that the transfer of steel to surface of a NiAlp/Al composite is higher, meanwhile, and the transfer of aluminum to the surface of steel (pin) is lower. At the applied load above 9.4 N, the NiAl particles are easy to fracture and become fragment, it can be seen that the coefficient of friction between steel and 10 pct NiAlp/Al composite is decreased with the applied load as shown in Fig. 2. the broken NiAl particles could not abrade steel at high wear rate. The transfer of Fe to the surface of NiAlp/Al composite is lower. As a result, the wear rate of steel at high loads become smaller.

CONCLUSIONS

At low loads, the wear resistance of SiCp/Al and 10 pct NiAlp/Al composites are about an order of magnitude better than that of unreinforced aluminum alloy, which is attributed by the fact that the particles support the applied load, prevent the soften aluminum matrix to wear directly with steel.

The wear rates of the SiCp/Al and NiAlp/Al composites increased to a levels comparable to that of unreinforced aluminum alloy at medium loads of 4.5 N to 9.4 N because of particle fracture and damage of subsurface crack layers.

The transition to severe wear takes place for unreinforced aluminum alloy at 13.5 N. However, no transition could be found for the SiCp/Al and NiAlp/Al composites due to their better yield strength at high temperature.

The SiCp/Al composite wore steel at the wear rate of 5-10 times of unreinforced aluminum alloy over the load applied because of the presence of hard particle. High volume fraction of SiC particle worn against steel at high wear rate.

At low applied loads, the NiAlp/Al composite worn against steel at higher wear rate than SiCp/Al composite. The wear rates of steel against the NiAlp/Al composite become the similar with that against the aluminum alloy when the NiAl particle is fractured at high loads above 13.5 N.

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